

MODELLING EFFECTS OF GEOMETRIC VARIABILITY ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 2D TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The state of the art analysis of textile composites allows one to adequately estimate their mechanical or permeability properties. Such analysis is usually based on an assumption of ideal periodicity i.e. on a unit cell representation of the textile composite [1]. Idealised unit cell geometry created in a geometrical pre-processor such as TexGen can be used for finite element (FE) analysis [2]. However, the internal structure of a textile composite does not possess ideal periodicity due to the presence of inevitable variabilities such as yarn waviness or ply nesting [3]. It has been previously argued that such variabilities as variation in yarn path affect fatigue strength [4] and variability of stacking angles affects stiffness of a laminate [5]. Study of these effects requires correct measurements and characterisations of variabilities for real textile composites. Measured statistical properties allow one to generate a statistically equivalent model of textile composites for further studies.

Methods of experimental characterisation of variabilities fall into two groups: meso-scale characterisation using small samples (usually of a unit cell size) and macro-scale characterisation using a large piece of a textile (or a composite). Olave [5] characterised textile reinforcements at the meso-scale using microscopy to obtain distributions of geometrical parameters of the textile reinforcement including nesting and overall composite thickness. The measured distributions were used for multiscale Monte Carlo analysis of laminate stiffness which appeared to be more dependent on variability of ply orientation and thickness than on yarn spacing. Nevertheless, the amount of experimentally analysed data leaves uncertainty in estimated distributions of geometrical parameters. Vanaershot [3] and Blacklock [6] used micro-CT characterisation of a

unit cell to gain statistical descriptors of woven reinforcements. A textile model was generated applying a Markov chain approach thus every yarn implements experimentally measured autocorrelation of the yarn. The main drawback of the approach is an assumption of the absence of long range distortions in the textile composite.

The analysis of optical images of a textile at the macroscale level was used by Endruweit [7] to characterise spacing between yarns and their waviness. The experimental distribution of spacing was used to generate a model of a bi-directional non-crimp textile for permeability analysis which showed that permeability is affected by the geometry disturbance and its variation is close to experimental variation. However, the yarn path was described by a predefined type of curve, all the layers were assumed to be the same and no correlation between neighbouring yarns was implemented. Skordos [8] used Fourier transform and correlation analysis of textile surface images to characterise the yarn path and its correlation on a large scale. A textile model was generated with use of the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck 2D process [9], which assumes a normal distribution of parameters and implements a Markov process using a covariance matrix which approximates the properties of the studied textile. The generated textile models were successfully used for stochastic simulations of forming processes showing the significance of a stochastic approach in simulation of manufacturing processes. Abdiwi [10] performed manual analysis of woven textiles and observed a significant long range variation of yarn path. The measured distributions of angle between warp and weft yarns were used for generation of a textile model using a genetic algorithm. The proposed algorithm suggested to model the systematic variation of a textile by an additional systematic

variation of yarn path expressed in terms of sine waves.

This study aims to use analysis of micro-CT and macro-images of textile reinforcement to obtain statistical. A generator of statistically equivalent (by means of deviation from an average path) textile reinforcement compatible with the TexGen pre-processor was developed. Monte Carlo simulations were used to predict mechanical properties of the textile composite with variability in yarn paths.

2 Manufacturing and mechanical experiments

The reinforcement used in this study was a balanced 2×2 twill weave textile of type 38391 by Carr Reinforcements with areal weight of 660g/m², nominal thickness 0.9mm and Grafil 34-700 12K carbon yarns woven with density of 4.2 picks per cm. Two types of 6-ply laminate with fibre volume fraction of 55% were manufactured using a RTM process using Gurit Prime 20LV epoxy resin. The first type of laminate had no control over the nesting between layers during the manufacturing process i.e. it had random stacking and random nesting. The second type of laminate was forced to have no nesting between layers. The preforms with no nesting were assembled on a table using metal pins to fix layers in chosen positions. Layers were bound together using NeoXil binder to prevent shift during the handling and RTM process.

Eight specimens of composite with random nesting and four with no nesting were manufactured and tested in tension according to EN ISO 527-4 standard using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) to measure strain. Additionally one specimen of every type was tested using ESPI (Electronic Speckle Pattern Interferometry). Results of mechanical testing are discussed and compared with numerically predicted properties in Section 6.

3 Geometrical characterisation of samples

The laminates' mesostructures were scanned using micro-CT with resolution of 15µm. Representative cross-sections are shown on Fig. 1. It can be seen that the goal of manufacturing samples with no nesting was not completely achieved because the top layer is shifted by approximately one half of a unit

cell. Fig.2 shows the strain field acquired with ESPI technique from the side with the correct lay-up. It can be seen that strain field on this side possesses a very clear periodic pattern compared to a composite with random nesting. Therefore, it can be deduced that the mistake in nesting of one layer is not significant for the strain field away from this layer.

Analysis of micro-CT of two samples with random nesting and one sample with no nesting allowed the creation of a statistically representative unit cell model of a twill weave textile composite by defining average properties such as yarn dimensions and path. Analysis of yarn shape showed that its closest approximation is a lenticular shape. The variability of yarn dimensions within the unit cell is not significant. The average yarn width is 2.491mm with standard deviation of 0.087mm and average yarn height is 0.352±0.024mm. It is worth noting that the latter variation is comparable with the precision of the measurements. Out-of-plane yarn path of all the yarns in every composite layer had difference of similar order as the resolution of micro-CT image which allows use of statistics from all the layers together to describe any layer. The in-plane variability of yarn path from the average yarn path is within a small range that can be mainly explained by tight weaving of the textile.

The macroscale structure of textile composites was investigated in three configurations. Three samples of dry textile of size 210×297mm were scanned with a flatbed image scanner with resolution of 1200dpi (i.e. 1pixel is 0.02mm). The same textiles were infused with the epoxy resin using VARTM and their surfaces were scanned. The outer surfaces of the 6-ply laminates were also scanned in order to compare their statistical properties with those of dry textiles and single layer composites.

A MATLAB program for automatic image analysis was developed to determine the yarn paths. The program was designed to analyse warp and weft yarns separately. The greyscale image of the whole textile was averaged, smoothed and then segmented by watershed algorithm in order to find points which lie within the yarns of interest. This information was used to crop subimages of yarn segments one by one. After that an image detection algorithm was applied to every subimage. The gradients in two orthogonal directions were used to

highlight edges of a yarn segment. A least squares fit was used to approximate edges of yarn segments with rectangles. The example of a subimage with detected edges and yarn segment approximation is shown in Fig. 3. The centres of the fitted rectangles were used to reconstruct yarn paths as shown in Fig. 4. The precision of automatic yarn segment detection is validated by comparing average width of segments and width of yarn measured by micro-CT. The automatically detected yarn width is 2.52 ± 0.056 mm which gives an acceptable precision for the automatic analysis method. The difference of about 0.03 mm between yarn width measured from the macro-image and that measured from micro-CT image is explained by lower width of yarns in the regions of intersection with other yarns which are not visible for optical acquisition.

The reconstructed yarn paths are shown in Fig. 5. These yarn paths were used to find an averaged yarn path by a simple averaging of all the positions along the length of textile. It can be seen that yarn paths of a dry textile have a notable waviness which results in a wavy average yarn path. The standard deviation of yarn paths from an average yarn path is only about 0.25 mm while the amplitude of variation for an individual yarn can be up to 1.0 mm (about 40% of the yarn width). The deviation of yarns from an average yarn path is shown in Fig. 6. It can be noticed that yarns have a similar path (i.e. strong correlation in perpendicular direction from yarn to yarn). In this particular textile tight weaving restricts yarns from moving independently. Therefore, a variation in one yarn causes variation of the neighbouring yarns to some extent.

Similar analysis was applied to single and multilayer composites. It was found that the standard deviation of yarns path from an average path in a single layer composites and 6-layer composites with random nesting were similar. The standard deviation for single layer composites and 6-ply composites are 0.24 mm and 0.20 mm respectively. In contrast, 6-layer composite without nesting exhibit lower variation of yarns path and its standard deviation is only about 0.15 mm. The difference between yarn path deviations of different types of reinforcement is close to the precision of automatic yarn path detection. It was also found that average yarn paths of laminates show lower amplitude of long-range waviness especially for the laminate without nesting.

The straightness of a yarn path in a laminate is explained by a careful straightening of yarns during manufacture and especially by the use of the pins to fix layers in a chosen position for laminates without nesting.

Correlation length in the yarn direction was calculated using Pearson's correlation between pairs of nodes spaced at a distance of k nodes as follows [11]:

$$C(k) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-k} d_i d_{i+k}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{n-k} (d_i)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{n-k} (d_{i+k})^2}} \quad (1)$$

where d_i is deviation from an average yarn path and n is a number of pairs. The graph of correlation length of weft yarns is shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen that a strong correlation (value above 0.5 [12]) of yarns path variability exists up to the length of 3-4 unit cells in both directions of dry textile. The autocorrelation of the yarn path allows the estimation of a period of self-repeat of the yarn path and a required size of a representative volume element of a composite for modelling of the yarn path variability.

4 Generation of models of textile composites with and without variabilities

The image analysis of micro-CT samples showed that yarn paths do not change significantly within a unit cell. The information obtained with micro-CT was used to create a representative volume element of an idealised textile composite i.e. a unit cell. Averaged properties of the textile have been used to reconstruct dimensions and paths of yarns within a unit cell using TexGen software. The unit cell of an idealised composite is shown in Fig. 8.

For creating a stochastic model of a textile reinforcement warp and weft yarns were assumed to be independent from each other. Each yarn was assumed to have a constant initial width and thickness determined by micro-CT analysis. The yarn paths were assumed to be defined by nodes on their centrelines. The Ornstein-Uhlenbeck 2D process [11] was applied to generate positions of centre-points of yarns in each direction. This process

is Gaussian, stationary and Markovian. The probability density function of the 2D Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process for a vector is expressed by [11]:

$$p(Z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^N \pi^N |\Sigma|}} \times \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (Z - \mu)^T \Sigma^{-1} (Z - \mu) \right\} \quad (2)$$

where N is the size of vector Z , Σ is the covariance matrix and μ is the vector of mean values.

The values of the covariance matrix were approximated to experimental data using the procedure described by Skordos [8]. The generated realisations of weft and warp yarns were used to create TexGen models. Small interpenetrations of yarns which can occur due to the variations of yarn paths were automatically corrected by applying a correction procedure which adjusts yarns dimensions and cross-section orientations.

5 Mechanical simulations

The geometrical models generated with TexGen were exported to Abaqus/Standard using a voxel mesh technique [13]. An idealised textile composite model without any variability was represented as a model of 3×3 unit cells with averaged statistical properties. Periodic boundary conditions were applied in the through thickness direction. Displacement in one in-plane direction and free surface in the other in-plane direction were applied. Yarns were assumed to be homogeneous transversely isotropic with elastic properties estimated using Chamis micromechanical formulae [14]. The properties of carbon fibres, matrix and yarns are listed in Table 1.

The models of the composite with yarns path variability were generated using Monte Carlo simulations with properties estimated from experimental data. Mechanical properties of textile composites with variability were found using 3×3 unit cells with periodic boundary conditions applied through thickness, displacement boundary conditions applied in one direction and free edges in the perpendicular direction.

6 Results and discussion

The predicted Young's modulus of the idealised textile composite was found to be 58.3 GPa which is 6% higher than the experimental value of 55±0.5GPa for a composite without nesting and 10% higher than the modulus of the composite with random nesting which is equal to 52.6±0.6GPa as listed in Table 2. The experimental Young's moduli contradict some experimental studies [15] on the nesting effect which reported that the Young's modulus of laminate with random nesting is higher than that of a laminate without nesting. However, this difference can be explained by the fact that yarn path variability of the composite without nesting was unintentionally controlled during the manufacturing process. The pins used to keep layers in the chosen positions restricted movement of yarns to some extent. Therefore, larger yarn misalignments in the composite with random nesting which were observed experimentally govern the Young's modulus reduction. Additionally, layer misorientation can have a similar effect while it was controlled in the composite without nesting.

The Monte Carlo simulations on composites with yarn paths variability yield a Young's modulus of 57.2±0.6GPa. The predicted value is 4% higher than experimental and has a similar standard deviation. The histogram of the Young's moduli distribution of 50 realisations is shown in Fig. 9. The upper limit of the histogram corresponds to the Young's modulus of the ideal composite.

7 Conclusions

This study investigates the influence of geometrical variabilities on the mechanical properties of a textile composite using numerical analysis. The investigations of geometry on two length scales allowed the estimation of geometry of the unit cell and of a larger sample of textile. The automatic image analysis of the woven structures allowed to determine an average yarn path of the textile reinforcement and to measure its variability. The statistically equivalent models of textile reinforcement were created using the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck random 2D process for every yarn direction. This process is Markovian and Gaussian

which corresponds to obtained textile geometric parameters.

The predicted mechanical properties of an idealised textile were higher than the measured properties of laminates of both types. Predicted properties of the textile composite with yarn path variability and no nesting were close to measured properties of the laminates of the same configuration. The predicted scatter of Young's modulus also was of the same order as the experimental value.

The conducted studies showed that the proposed methodology for measuring and modelling yarn paths variability is able to correctly predict the variation of the Young' modulus of textile composites. The proposed framework can be used for modelling the effects variability of reinforcement on other mechanical properties and on reinforcement permeability. The future work will include strength prediction of the laminate with yarn path and nesting variability.

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References

[1] Lomov SV, Huysmans G, Luo Y, Parnas RS, Prodromou A, Verpoest I, Phelan FR. Textile composites: modelling strategies. *Compos Pt A-Appl Sci Manuf.* 2001;32(10):1379-1394.
 [2] Ivanov DS, Baudry F, Van Den Broucke B, Lomov SV, Xie H, Verpoest I. Failure analysis of triaxial braided composite. *Compos Sci Technol.* 2009;69(9):1372-1380.
 [3] Vanaerschot A, Cox BN, Lomov SV, Vandepitte D. Stochastic framework for quantifying the geometrical variability of laminated textile composites using micro-computed tomography. *Compos Pt A-Appl Sci Manuf.* 2013;44:122-131.
 [4] Dadkhah MS, Cox BN, Morris WL. Compression-Compression Fatigue of 3d

Woven Composites. *Acta Metallurgica Et Materialia.* 1995;43(12):4235-4245.

[5] Olave M, Vanaerschot A, Lomov SV, Vandepitte D. Internal geometry variability of two woven composites and related variability of the stiffness. *Polym Composite.* 2012;33(8):1335-1350.

[6] Blacklock M, Bale H, Begley M, Cox B. Generating virtual textile composite specimens using statistical data from micro-computed tomography: 1D tow representations for the Binary Model. *J Mech Phys Solids.* 2012;60(3):451-470.

[7] Endruweit A, Long AC. Influence of stochastic variations in the fibre spacing on the permeability of bi-directional textile fabrics. *Compos Pt A-Appl Sci Manuf.* 2006;37(5):679-694.

[8] Skordos AA, Sutcliffe MPF. Stochastic simulation of woven composites forming. *Compos Sci Technol.* 2008;68(1):283-296.

[9] Henderson D, Plaschko P. Stochastic differential equations in science and engineering: World Scientific Pub.; 2006.

[10] Abdiwi F, Harrison P, Koyama I, Yu WR, Long AC, Corriea N, Guo Z. Characterising and modelling variability of tow orientation in engineering fabrics and textile composites. *Compos Sci Technol.* 2012;72(9):1034-1041.

[11] Gardiner CW. Handbook of stochastic methods for physics, chemistry, and the natural sciences. 3rd ed. Berlin: New York: Springer-Verlag; 2004.

[12] Grimmett G, Stirzaker D. Probability and Random Processes: Clarendon Press; 2001.

[13] Kim HJ, Swan CC. Voxel-based meshing and unit-cell analysis of textile composites. *Int J Numer Methods Eng.* 2003;56(7):977-1006.

[14] Chamis CC. Mechanics of Composite-Materials - Past, Present, and Future. *J Compos Tech Res.* 1989;11(1):3-14.

[15] Ito M, Chou TW. An analytical and experimental study of strength and failure behavior of plain weave composites. *J Compos Mater.* 1998;32(1):2-30.

Fig. 1. Micro-CT images of laminates without nesting (left) and with random nesting (right)

Fig. 2. Distribution of longitudinal strain as measured by ESPI in laminate without nesting (left) and in laminate with random nesting (right)

Fig. 3. Edge detection of yarn segment

Fig. 4. Approximated yarns paths

Fig. 5. Example of yarn path of weft yarns of dry textile

Fig. 6. Average weft yarn path and deviation of yarns from it

Fig. 7. Correlation length of weft yarns

Fig. 8. An idealised unit cell of 2x2 twill weave textile reinforcement and its FE model

Fig. 9. Histogram of predicted Young's moduli

Table 1. Materials properties

	E_1 , GPa	$E_2=E_3$, GPa	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	$G_{12}=G_{13}$, GPa	G_{23} , GPa
Matrix	3.1	3.1	0.35	0.35	1.15	1.15
Fibre	234	15	0.20	0.25	13.0	6.0
Yarn ($V_f = 77\%$)	181.1	9.35	0.23	0.35	5.76	3.05

Table 2. Experimental and predicted Young's moduli of textile composites, GPa

Predicted idealised	Predicted with variability	Experimental without nesting	Experimental random nesting
58.3	57.3 ± 0.64	55 ± 0.5	52 ± 0.5